

LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AS A FACTOR OF INCREASING COMPETITIVENESS.

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G'ijduvon tuman 1-son kasb-hunar maktabi umumta'lim fani o'qituvchisi

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Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy mutaxassislarning xorijiy tillarni bilishi ularning mehnat bozoridagi raqobatbardoshligini oshiruvchi muhim omillardan biri ekanligi ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: xorijiy til, raqobatbardoshlik, chet tilida so'zlashuv va kommunikatsiya.

Аннотация:

В данной статье рассматривается, что знание иностранных языков современными специалистами является одним из важных факторов, повышающих их конкурентоспособность на рынке труда.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, конкурентоспособность, иноязычное общение и общение.

Annotation:

In this article, it is considered that the knowledge of foreign languages of modern specialists is one of the important factors that increase their competitiveness in the labor market.

Key words: foreign language, competitiveness, foreign language speaking and communication.

Over the past decades our world has become more independent and new technologies have allowed us to work in close contact with people all over the world. As relationships with countries grow, so does the need to speak a foreign language. We have an enhanced need for an enlightened citizenship that is both culturally and linguistically prepared to function in today's world.

Learning a foreign language is not an easy thing. It is a long and slow process that takes a lot of time and efforts. Nowadays it is especially important to know foreign languages. Some people learn languages because they need them for their work, others travel abroad, for the third studying languages is a hobby. Everyone, who knows foreign languages can speak to people from other countries, read foreign writers in the original, which makes your outlook wider. It is not surprising that many intellectuals and well-educated people are polyglots. I study English. Nowadays English has become the world's most important language in politics, science, trade and cultural relations. Over 300 million people speak it as a m

other tongue. The native speakers of English live in Great Britain, the United States of America, Australia and New Zealand. English is one of the official languages in the Irish Republic, Canada, the South Africa Republic. English is one of the official languages of the United Nations Organization and other political organizations. Half of the world's scientific literature is in English. It is the language of computer technology. To know English today is absolutely necessary for every educated person, for every good specialist.

After the theoretical research we can offer the definition of the competitiveness concept. Competitiveness is an integrative totality of an individual's qualities (qualities of a personality and a specialist) that ensures its viability, including development and self-actualization, under the conditions of changing environment. The competitive personality is characterized by the following qualities/features: 1) characterizing indicators of a personality orientation and self-conception, including determination and action oriented towards success; readiness to overcome difficulties and take a risk; persistence, adequate self-assessment and daring to take a risk; 2) well-developed selfregulation, including volition, stress endurance, self-reflection, including analytical-evaluating and systemic thinking; personality's flexibility (flexibility in thinking, emotional sphere, behaviour), the ability to make a decision; the responsibility for the made decisions and their consequences; 3) different competences, including professional competences and creativity as an ability, oneself- (ego-) and environment- (eco-) oriented friendly thinking, attitude and behaviour: observation of moral and ethical principles, principles of environmental, including social environment (community), balance and sustainability, readiness for co-operation with other people; 4) readiness to change oneself in order to maintain the balance with the changing environment, readiness to start changes in the environment on the basis of environment-friendly attitude and action.

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